
A Critical Study on the Recent Research Contribution of Vice-chancellors of Selected Private Universities in India

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Abstract

India, being the second highest in the number of private universities in the World, has given exactly 50 % shares to privately governed Universities (Private & Deemed to be universities together) and remaining 50% are Govt. Funded universities (Central & State Govt. together). Presently in India, there are 264 private universities spread over 22 states. Along with providing latest industry-oriented higher education training and placement, private universities are also have the challenge to involve both students and faculties in innovative research in order to increase the research output. While discussing the challenges of increasing the research productivity in organizations, recently proposed Theory of Accountability (Theory A) suggests the strategy of showing 'Role models' in the organizations to the researchers so that the target of each and every researcher can be substantially increased with the slogan – 'It is Possible'. In this paper, we have proposed the responsibility of Vice-chancellors as Role models for researchers to boost the research output of the universities by adding self-contribution of them in the form of research publications. In this regard, we have studied the contribution of Vice-chancellors to present them as Role models to researchers in private universities due to their less administrative responsibilities compared to public university Vice-chancellors in India. The research contributions in the form of published papers in journals for the last 5 years is tabulated, analysed, and discussed to see the Role model characteristics and is compared with an optimistic estimate, realistic estimate, and pessimistic estimate of our theoretical prediction.

Keywords : Research contribution, Research performance, Vice-chancellor, Private universities, Role model, Leader.

1. INTRODUCTION :

One of the objectives of higher education is creating new knowledge through innovative research. Further, this new knowledge has to transfer to the industry and the society in order to improve the

performance and quality of various products and services or to solve the problems in the society. Thus Research and publication is an integral part of higher education institutions including universities. Many of universities all over the world promoted themselves as research universities as their objectives leads to focus on research along with providing higher education to the students through improving their knowledge, skills, attitude, and confidence [1-10]. The challenge for the universities world over is how to formulate a strategy to motivate and engage their faculty members and students in research and publications. In this regard, many universities have offered different types of supports and incentives to encourage the faculties to engage in research and publications. Accordingly, various metrics are developed to measure the faculty research performance and also various theories are developed to monitor and boost performance [11- 12]. Research and publication is an important parameter for universities brand building through national and international ranking system [13-16]. Currently one of the parameters used in many university ranking scores is their research contribution in terms of faculty publications. Research performance index of both faculty members and the higher education institutions are used in ranking the faculty and institutions [17-24]. This further pressurized the universities to focus on research and publications by providing required infrastructure and resources for boosting research activities. The question is to know from where the research culture should start in Universities and other higher education institutions and also whether it is from top to bottom or from bottom to top levels in the organizations. While discussing the challenges of increasing the research productivity in organizations, recently proposed Theory of Accountability (Theory A) suggests the strategy of showing 'role models' in the organization to the researchers [25-30] so that the target of each and every researcher can be substantially increased with the slogan – 'It is Possible'. In this paper, we made an attempt to study the recent contributions of Vice-chancellors to research and publications as Role models to other researchers by considering a segment of universities called Private universities in India. This also examines the responsibilities of Vice-chancellors to motivate and stimulate individuals and group researchers in their organization while doing their administrative responsibilities as head of the university. The research result checks the attitude of senior professors or educators in their commitment to their original profession that is teaching and research along with their major responsibility of administration of university affairs [31-39]. In this methodology of testing the theoretical predicted model based on UGC regulations of Ph.D. guideship norms. Here, the research contribution in the form of published papers in journals for the last 5 years is tabulated, analysed, and discussed to see the Role model characteristics and is compared with an optimistic estimate, realistic estimate, and pessimistic estimate of our theoretical prediction [40-41].

2. PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN INDIA :

Many Countries around the globe have adopted private University system as a part of their higher education offering strategy. India, being second highest in the number of private universities in the World, has given exactly 50 % shares to privately governed Universities (Private & Deemed to be universities together) and remaining 50% are Govt. Funded universities (Central & State Govt. together). Presently in India, there are 264 private universities spread over 22 states. Due to non-availability of any financial support from the state and central governments, private universities are trying to sustain through their only strategy of service differentiation through 21st century curriculum and industry integrated programme design [42-46]. Many private universities are owned by industrialists and supported by their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funds. As a result, Private universities are trying to get good, eminent faculty members and administrators to attract maximum students from different states and even from abroad. Many private universities are focusing on research and publication by appointing research background faculties in all cadres to grab top ranks in NIRF University rankings and top grade in NAAC Assessments & Accreditations. This strategy leads to the appointment of eminent researchers as Research Deans or even as Vice-chancellors of the universities. The expectation behind such strategies is being the eminent researchers with good the number of publications record, Vice-chancellors may be motivators and role models for other faculty members to develop the research culture in the university. The relative freeness of Vice-chancellors in

terms of time, in private universities compared to Government sponsored public universities, they can focus a part of their time in research and publications if they have such talent, interest, and intention. This paper focuses on studying the attitude of Vice-chancellors in private universities towards research and publication by mingling with many research teams in their university. This is done by studying their research publications during last 5 years.

3. THEORY A & IMPORTANCE OF ROLE-MODEL IN RESEARCH PERFORMANCE :

Theory A is proposed during 2017 to account time progress on earlier theories on organizational behaviour due to changes in technology, human aspirations, economical & social conditions, and environmental knowledge. Theory A made an attempt to address the challenges of existing propositions on human behaviour and motivation in organizations by presenting new propositions to enhance organizational productivity. By providing better insights on current organizational perspectives it considered the competitive environment and changed employee mindset of the modern society of 21st century which have undergone enormous changes due to changes in technology and means of production, production relations, customer and societal perception and one's own expectations. Theory A considered the quest for creativity, propels the employee to contribute to the organization drawing positive energy from his innate potential and tuned to best performance models around him through self-exploration while developing its propositions. Theory A is a management strategy which believes in fulfilling its own objectives for enhancement of output by making its people delivering targets as responsibility, feeling of creativity and contribution for motivation, identifying with the organization as commitment and accountability as a hallmark of efficiency. Essential components of Theory of Accountability (Theory A) are : (1) Planning, (2) Target setting, (3) Motivation, (4) Work Strategies, (5) Responsibility, (6) Role model, (7) Monitoring & Guiding, and (8) Accountability [25-30, 47]. The Role model component of Theory A is tested in this study by checking the possibility of considering Vice-chancellors as Role models in research institutions by collecting the recent research publications of Vice-chancellors of private universities.

4. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY :

The objective of this paper is to study the individual research contribution of Vice-chancellors as role models to faculty researchers in private universities. This also checks the responsibility of Vice-chancellors to motivate young researchers to focus and contribute to research and publications respectively so as to full fill one of the objectives of the organization. It also include to determine logically the intensity of involvement of such high calibre professors appointed as Vice-chancellors in universities and hence to estimate the optimistic number of research publications per year, Realistic number of publications per year with other administrative responsibilities, and the pessimistic number of publications when various supporting situations are against the expected plan.

The publication data are collected during the last week of March 2018 using Google scholar search facility for 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 separately using Custom range search facility of Google scholar website - <https://scholar.google.co.in/>. Care is taken to avoid mix of data of different authors of same name. Publication data of four years three months is effectively collected for study and comparison. Five years research index is calculated by adding journal publications for all five years and dividing the sum by five. The **Five years Research Index** is only representative and measures the five years research productivity of individual Vice-chancellor.

5. RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION OF CURRENT VICE-CHANCELLORS OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES :

The research contributions of current Vice-chancellors who are the administrative and academic heads of private universities are determined during last five years. As per general opinion, in public universities, the Vice-chancellors are appointed based on various factors including, the present government policies, reservation policies, and various other unspecified policies & priorities along

with academic, administrative and research abilities of the candidates, whereas, in private universities, it is purely on merits of the candidates in terms of proven records in administration and research abilities. This section makes an attempt on creating a theoretical expectation on contribution of Vice-chancellors in private universities in terms of research and publications. The theoretical expectations are further verified by studying the research output (in terms of journal publications) of Vice-chancellors of private universities in India for the last five years.

5.1 Theoretical Expectations :

In private universities, the administrative responsibilities of Vice-chancellors are comparatively less due to the fact that many of financial related administrative decisions are the responsibilities of the Chancellors and Pro-chancellors unlike the situation in Public Universities. Usually, every private university considers its Vice-chancellor as Role-model for every employee of the organization due to his/her all-round and multi-tasking personality. Vice-chancellors in Private Universities are expected to be good teachers, eminent researchers who guide and motivate all researchers, and inspire all faculty members in the Universities. In order to attract more committed students and faculty members at all levels, the private university should follow a strategy by appointing an all-rounder, role-model as its leader, i.e., an active Vice-chancellor. To support this argument a model is proposed using Theory A – Organizational Accountability theory for 21st century with following postulates :

RESEARCHER
Creative - Innovator
Experienced Academician
Established Researcher
Team Player
Role Model - Students & Teachers

Postulate 1 : Innovator - A Vice-chancellor is an young, energetic, enthusiastic, & eminent person who is dare to think beyond the obvious. He should have innovative development vision and innovative research vision.

Postulate 2 : Experienced Academician - A Vice-chancellor being head of the university should be Experienced, Acclaimed Teacher who can fill confidence among stakeholders. – Ideal Academician.

Postulate 3 : Established Researcher - A Vice-chancellor being head of the research university should have strong track of research and contribution to his field of expertise and should have created a niche in terms of developing new theories, models, concepts, methods, and/or analysis framework.

Postulate 4 : Effective Administrator - A Vice-chancellor should be an able administrator to implement the mission of the university. He/She should know how to implement plans and strategies by involving every stakeholder and evaluating their accountability.

Postulate 5 : All-round Leader - A Vice-chancellor should be an all round leader who can inspire & motivate every stakeholders of the university by showing their responsibilities and training them to achieve their individual and organizational goal. As an all-round researcher, he should be a team player motivating and guiding many teams of researchers for increasing university research output.

Figure 1 : Model connects the characteristics of an Ideal Vice-chancellor for any type of Universities.

Postulate 6 : Global Diplomat : A Vice-chancellor who can develop global partnerships, collaborations, synergies both in research and placements through his International Experience & Networking contacts.

Postulate 7 : Role Model : A Vice-chancellor should be able to do the things effectively and differently in university affairs to prove that **IT IS POSSIBLE** to his/her stakeholders. Being Role Model is very important characteristics of a leader and even for Vice-chancellor so that he has a right to expect such performance from everybody in the organization.

It is also argued that compared to the responsibilities of Vice-chancellors of Public universities which are more slanted towards the administrative side, the responsibilities of Vice-chancellors in private universities are slanted towards research and development. For example, the Vice-chancellor of Shiv Nadar University also has an additional charge of Dean – Research to focus on research which is the major objective of the University. In comparison of the responsibilities of Vice-chancellors of public and private universities based on their focus on administrative and research responsibilities.

Table 1 : Comparison of the responsibilities of Vice-chancellors of Public and Private Universities.

S. No.	Parameter	Public University	Private University
1	Administrative	More	Less
2	Academic	Less	More
3	Research & Publication	Less	More
4	Brand Building	Less	More
5	Training	Medium	Medium
6	Networking/ Collaboration	Less	More
7	Expansion	Less	More
8	Leadership & Role model	Less	More
9	Innovation in Higher Education	Medium	More

Table 2 : Expected annual research output of Vice-chancellors based on realistic estimate

S. No.	Expected Collaboration	Expected annual research publications – Realistic Estimate
1	Along with his/her Ph.D. Scholars	06

2	Along with M.Phil./M.Tech. Scholars	04
3	Along with collaborative research teams	04
4	Along with International research teams	02
5	Total/year	14 papers
	Total/5 years	70 papers
	Expected 5 Years Research Index	14

As per table 2, the realistic prediction of minimum papers to be published by a Vice-chancellor is 14. On the other hand, the optimum prediction and pessimistic predictions are given in table 3 which gives the possible maximum research papers to be published as per optimistic papers estimate and minimum research papers to be published as per pessimistic paper estimate respectively. In optimistic number estimate, by considering 2 papers publications each with six Ph.D. research scholars, 2 papers publications each with four M.Phil./M.Tech. students and four papers with internal University groups and four papers with Foreign research groups per year lead to 30 papers per year.

Table 3 : Expected annual research output of Vice-chancellors in optimistic and pessimistic estimate.

S. No.	Expected Collaboration	Expected annual research publications – Optimistic Estimate	Expected annual research publications – Pessimistic Estimate
1	Along with his/her Ph.D. Scholars	12	03
2	Along with M.Phil./M.Tech. Scholars	08	02
3	Along with collaborative research teams	06	02
4	Along with International research teams	04	02
5	Total/year	30	09
6	Total/5 years	150	27
7	Expected 5 Years Research Index	30	9

The above research publication estimates are made for Vice-chancellors by duly considering their administrative responsibilities. Accordingly, Vice-chancellors who publish 30 and more papers per year belongs to a category of **Super Researchers**, Vice-chancellors who publish 14 and more papers per year belongs to a category of **Excellent Researchers**, and Vice-chancellors who publish 09 and more papers per year belongs to a category of **Good Researchers**. For example, Dr. CNR Rao of Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research, Bangalore, India [48] falls on Super Researcher category.

5.3 Actual Performance Based on the Collected Data :

The publication data of Vice-chancellors of various private universities state-wise are collected during the last week of March 2018 using Google scholar search facility for 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 separately using Custom range search facility of Google scholar website - <https://scholar.google.co.in/>. Care is taken to avoid mix of data of different authors of same name. Publication data of four years three months is effectively collected for study and comparison. The collected data on research publications are further checked either Vice-chancellors personal web site/blog or their university website. Five years research index is calculated by adding journal publications for all five years and dividing the sum by five. The **Five years Research Index** is only representative and measures the five years research productivity of individual Vice-chancellor. The research publications (year-wise) and the five years research index of Vice-chancellors of Indian private universities are tabulated State-wise as shown in tables 4 to 22.

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Table 4 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Karnataka state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Alliance University Dr. Pavana Dibbur	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Azim Premji University Mr. Anurag Behar	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	CMR University Dr. M. S. Shivakumar	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Dayananda Sagar University Dr. A. N. N. Murthy	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	JSS Science & Technology University Dr. B.G. Sangameshwara	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	KLE Technological University Dr. Ashok S. Shettar	0	02	01	2	1	6/5 = 1.2
7	M.S. Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences Dr. S. R. Shankapal	0	0	0	01	0	0.2
8	PES University Dr. K.N.B. Murthy	09	07	06	03	02	27/5= 5.04
9	Presidency University Dr. Nagendra Parashar	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Rai Technology University Dr. Rupa Vasudevan	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Reva University Dr.S. Y. Kulkarni	05	03	01	01	0	10/5= 2.0
12	Srinivas University Dr. P. S. Aithal	07	50	82	73	33	245/5= 49.0

Table 5 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Gujarat state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Ahmedabad University Dr. Pankaj Chandra	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	AURO University of Hospitality and Management Dr. Avadhesh Kumar Singh	0	01	0	1	0	2/5= 0.4
3	Charotar University of Science & Technology Dr. Patel B.G.	04	0	05	0	02	11/5= 2.2

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4	Dhirubhai Ambani Institute of Information and Communication Technology Dr. K.S. Dasgupta	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Ganpat University Dr. Mahendra Sharma	0	0	0	01	0	1/5= 0.2
6	Institute of Advanced Research Dr. G N Magesan	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	Navrachana University Dr. Abir Mullick	0	0	0	1	0	1/5 = 0.2
8	Nirma University Dr Anup K. Singh	01	02	01	01	0	5/5=1.0
9	Pandit Deendayal petroleum University Dr. T. Kishen Kumar Reddy	05	01	0	06	0	12/5= 2.4
10	Parul University Dr Ketan Kotecha	02	05	02	03	02	14/5=2.8
11	RK University Dr. T. R. Desai	01	01	02	0	0	4/5=0.8
12	UKA Tarsadia University Dr. Dinesh R. Shah	0	02	0	0	0	2/5=0.4

Table 6 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Maharashtra state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Amity University Dr. V V Khole	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Mody University of Science & Technology	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	Spicer Adventist University Noble Prasad Pilli	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Rajasthan state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Amity University Dr. Shishir K. Dube	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Bhagwant University Dr. V K Sharma	0	0	0	2	0	2/5 =0.4
3	Career Point University Dr. D.N. Rao	1	1	0	2	0	4/5 = 0.8

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4	Dr K N Modi University Dr. Vinod Kumar	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Geetanjali University	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	ICFAI University Dr.P.B.L.Chaurasia	09	02	0	0	0	11/5= 2.2
7	Jagannath University Dr. V K Agarwal	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	JK Lakshmi Pat University Dr. R.L Raina,	1	0	1	0	1	3/5=0.6
9	Jodhpur National University D. K. Mehta	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Madhav University Prof. J. L. Vij	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology Dr. M.C Misra	0	1	0	1	0	2/5=0.4
12	Manipal University Dr G K Prabhu Dr. H. P. Khincha	1 (2)	0 (1)	0 (2)	2 (1)	0 0	3/5=0.6 6/5 = 1.2
13	Mewar University Dr. Ashok Kumar Gadiya	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	NIIT University Dr. V.S. Rao	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	NIMS University Dr. Balvir S. Tomar	1	0	02	0	0	3/5 = 0.6
16	Poornima University Dr. K.K.S. Bhatia	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	Shridhar University	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 8 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Uttar Pradesh state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	AMITY University Dr. B. Shukla	05	01	04	02	1	13/5 = 2.6
2	Babu Banarasi Das University Dr. Arun Kumar Mittal	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Bennett University Dr. Raghunath K. Shevgaonkar	2	0	0	0	0	2/5=0.2
4	Galgotias University Dr. Jayasankar Variyar	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	IFTM University Ashoke K. Ghosh	3	08	1	1	0	13/5 = 2.6
6	Integral University Dr.M.K.J. Siddiqui	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	Invertis University	0	0	1	0	0	0.2

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	Dr. Jagdish Rai						
8	Jaypee University Dr. Rajiv Saxena	09	07	02	03	01	22/5= 4.04
9	Mangalayatan University Dr. P. S. Siwach	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Noida International University Dr. K.K. Dewan	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Sharda University Dr. Brishbhan Singh Panwar	0	1	0	0	0	1/5=0.2
12	Shiv Nadar University Dr. Rupamanjari Ghosh	03	01	01	0	0	5/5=1
13	Teerthanker Mahaveer University Dr. Rakesh Kr. Mudgal	0	0	0	0		0

Table 9 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Punjab state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Chandigarh University Dr. R. S. Bawa	0	0	01	0	01	2/5=0.4
2	Chitkara University Dr. Archana Mantri,	2	07	01	04	0	14/5 =2.8
3	D.A.V University Dr. Rakesh Kumar Mahajan	18	09	06	06	04	43/5=8.6
4	Guru Kashi University Dr. B. S. Dhaliwal	01	01	01	01	0	4/5=0.8
5	Lovely Professional University Dr. Ramesh Kanwar	0	0	0	01	0	1/5=0.2
6	Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University Dr. Sukhdarshan Singh Khehra	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 10 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of West Bengal state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Techno India University	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	Amity University Dr. Gurinder Singh	0	2	1	0	0	3/5

Table 11 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Haryana state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	

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1	AMITY University Dr. P.B. Sharma Dr. Padmakali Banerjee	0	1	0	0	0	1/5=0.2
2	Ansal University Dr. Raj Singh	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Ashoka University Dr. Pratap Bhanu Mehta	1	0	0	0	1	2/5=0.4
4	BML Munjal University Dr. B. S. Satyanarayana	0	0	1	0	0	1/5=0.2
5	GD Goenka University Dr. Shrihari	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	K.R. Mangalam University Dr. R.K. Mittal	2	1	0	0	0	3/5=0.6
7	M.V.N. University Dr. J.V. Desai	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Manav Rachna University Dr. Sanjay Srivastava	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	O.P. Jindal Global University Dr. C. Raj Kumar	0	1	0	0	0	1/5=0.2
10	Shree Guru Gobind Singh Tricentenary University Dr. A. K. S. Suryavanshi	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	SRM University Dr. P. Prakash	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	The Northcap University Dr. H B Raghavendra	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 12 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Madhya Pradesh state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Amity University Lt Gen VK Sharma	0	0	0	0	0	
2	ITM University Dr. Kamal Kant Dwivedi	0	1	0	0	0	0
3	Jaypee University of Engineering & Technology Dr. J.S.P. Rai	0	1	0	0	0	1/5=0.2
4	Oriental University Dr. Dhruva Ghai	1	1	1	0	0	3/5=0.6
5	People's University Dr. V.K. Pandya.	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Sri Satya Sai University of Technology & Medical Sciences Dr. R. P. Singh	0	0	3	8	4	15/5=3
7	Swami Vivekananda University Dr. N. K. Thapak	0	0	0	0	0	0

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Table 13 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Uttarakhand state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	DIT University Dr. Kuldeep K Raina	0	1	0	2	0	3/5=0.6
2	Hingiri Zee University Dr. Rakesh Ranjan	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	IMS Unison University Dr. Rajendra Kumar Pandey	0	1	0	0	0	1/5=0.2
4	The ICFAI University Dr. Pawan K. Aggarwal	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies Dr Deependra Kumar Jha	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Uttaranchal University Dr. N.K. Joshi	0	0	1	0	0	0
7	University of Patanjali Acharya Balakrishna	5	6	18	11	3	43/5=8.6

Table 14 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Chhattisgarh state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Amity University Raj S. Dhankar	12	8	8	9	0	37/5= 7.4
2	Dr. C.V. Raman University Dr. Ravi Prakash Dubey	0	4	2	1	0	7/5=1.4
3	ICFAI University Dr. Satyendra P Gupta	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	ITM University Dr. Sanjay Kumar,	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Kalinga University Dr. Jagannath Patnaik	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	MATS University Dr. Byju John	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	O.P. Jindal University Dr PRABHU AGGARWAL	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 15 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Orissa state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Centurion University of Technology and Management Dr. Haribandhu Panda	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Sri Sri University	0	0	0	1	0	1/5=0.2

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	Dr Nand Lal						
3	Xavier university Dr. Fr. Paul Fernandes, S.J	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Birla Global University Dr. Sudhakar Panda	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 16 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Meghalaya state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	CMJ University	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	Martin Luther Christian University Dr. Vincent T. Darlong	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	University of Science & Technology Prof. P. G. Rao	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	University of Technology & Management Dr. Mukesh Saxena	1	2	1	1	0	5/5=1
5	William Carey University Prof. Ken Gnanakan	0	2	0	0	2	4/5=0.8

Table 17 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Assam state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Assam Don Bosco University Dr. Stephen Mavelly	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Assam Down Town University Dr. Amarjyoti Choudhury	17	5	1	1	0	24/5=4.8
3	The Assam Kaziranga University Dr. P K Mishra	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 18 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Sikkim state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Eastern Institute for Integrated Learning in Management University Dr. R. P. Banerjee	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Shri Ramasamy Memorial University, Sikkim Dr. N. Sethuraman	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Sikkim Manipal University	0	0	0	0	0	0

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	Lt. Gen. (Dr) Venkatesh						
4	ICFAI University Prof. Jagannath Patnaik	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Vinayaka Missions Sikkim University Dr. D. D. Kaushik	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 19 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Arunachal Pradesh state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Apex Professional University Dr. A.A. Dange	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Arunachal University of Studies Dr. V.K. Kawatra	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Arunodaya University Dr. Vishwa Nath Sharma	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Himalayan University Dr. S. P. Singh.	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Indira Gandhi Technological and Medical Science University	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	North East Frontier Technical University	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Venkateshwara Open University	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 20 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Nagaland state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	The Global Open University Dr. H N Dutta	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	The Institute of Chartered Financial Analysts of India University Dr. Charles P. Alexander	1	0	0	0	0	0.2

Table 21 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Jharkhand state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	Jharkhand Rai University Dr. Savita Sengar	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Sai Nath University	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	The Institute of Chartered Financial Analysts of India	2	0	4	2	0	8/5=1.6

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	University Prof. O R S Rao,						
4	Pragyan International University Dr. Suresh Kumar Agarwal,	0	0	1	0	0	1/5 =0.2
5	Amity University	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 22 : Research Publications of Vice-chancellors of Private Universities of Himachal Pradesh state

S.No	University & Name of Vice-chancellor	Number of Research Papers published in Journals					Five years Research Index
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018*	
1	A P Goyal Shimla University Dr. Tej Pratap	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Abhilashi University Dr. Amar Singh Guleria	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Arni University Brig S C Verma	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Baddi University of Emerging Sciences & Technology Dr. T.R. Bhardwaj	5	7	2	6	0	20/5= 4
5	Bahra University Dr. Satish Kumar	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Career Point University Dr. D.N. Rao	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	Chitkara University Dr. Varinder S. Kanwar	0	0	0	0	0	
8	Eternal University Dr. H. S. Dhaliwal	3	7	6	11	3	30/5= 6
9	I.E.C. (India Education Centre) University Dr. Mahaveer Singh	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Indus International University Dr. Satish Menon	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Jaypee University of Information Technology Dr. Vinod Kumar	32	34	10	2	3	81/5=16.2
12	Maharaja Agrasen University Dr. Rakesh Kumar Gupta	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	Maharishi Markandeshwar University	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	Manav Bharti University Dr. Jitendra Nath Shrivastava	0	0	0	0	0	0

15	Shoolini University of Biotechnology and Management Sciences Prof. P.K. Khosla	1	0	1	1	0	3/5= 0.6
16	Sri Sai University Dr. S.K. Kaushal	0	0	0	0	0	0

The states like Bihar, Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura, do not yet have private universities.

5.4 Findings :

Based on our observation, out of 145 working private universities, 57 Vice-chancellors have published at least one paper during last 5 years (40 %), 24 Vice-chancellors have published average one paper per year, 19 Vice-chancellors have published average two papers per year, 11 Vice-chancellors have published three or more papers per year, 10 Vice-chancellors have published four or more papers per year and 07 Vice-chancellors have published five or more papers per year and 5 Vice-chancellors have published close to nine papers per year to **Good Researcher Grade**, 2 Vice-chancellors have published more than fourteen papers per year and received **Excellent Researcher Grade**, and one Vice-chancellors has published more than thirty papers per year and reached **Super Researcher Grade**. The results are tabulated in table 23.

Table 23 : Average publications of last five years of Vice-chancellors of private universities in India

S. No.	Average Publications per year	No. of Vice-chancellors out of 145	Percentage
1	0	88	60 %
2	1 and more	57	40 %
3	2 and more	19	13 %
4	3 and more	11	7.5 %
5	4 and more	10	7 %
6	5 and more	07	5 %
7	9 and more	05	3 % (Good)
8	14 and more	02	1.4 % (Excellent)
9	30 and more	01	0.7 % (Super)

6. CONCLUSION :

As per Theory A, one of the components which can boost the organization performance is target setting by showing Role model. The contribution of Role model to organizational activities will inspire other employees to redefine their goal by believing the slogan 'It is possible'. In higher education institutions like universities, the Vice-chancellors should play the role of Role model in order to boost the research contribution of the university. This is because Vice-chancellors are usually chosen from the fraternity of eminent professors who have already contributed to the academics and research during their service and are experienced research supervisors guided many Ph.D. students. With this background, we have studies the research contribution of Vice-chancellors of private universities of India for last five years to enquire the possibilities of considering them as Role models for the researchers of their Universities. The result is not encouraging and in many cases, Vice-chancellors are not published even one paper in national or international journals. The results are not favourable. Many Vice-chancellors (60%) have not published even one research paper during last five years due to various reasons discussed in the paper. They have not shown accountability probably due to the reason that Vice-chancellorship is the last assignment in their life.

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